

These are the pieces that make the old positive valued linguistics time travelling clock:

The positive winner hands:

- Level 36 positive, the nothing seen winner auto-zero hand.
- Level 35 positive, the something hidden winner auto-equal hand.
- Level 34 positive, the 1st seen winner auto-amount hand.
- Level 33 positive, the 2nd hidden winner auto-sum hand.
- Level 32 positive, the 3rd seen winner auto-fill hand.

The positive finalist hands:

- Level 31 positive, the last final hidden auto-symbol hand.
- Level 30.3 positive, the outer seen outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 30.2 positive, the outer seen middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 30.1 positive, the outer seen inner auto-symbol hand.
- Level 29.3 positive, the outer hidden outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 29.2 positive, the outer hidden middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 29.1 positive, the outer hidden inner auto-symbol hand.
- Level 28.3 positive, the middle seen outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 28.2 positive, the middle seen middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 28.1 positive, the middle seen inner auto-symbol hand.
- Level 27.3 positive, the middle hidden outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 27.2 positive, the middle hidden middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 27.1 positive, the middle hidden inner auto-symbol hand.
- Level 26.3 positive, the inner seen outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 26.2 positive, the inner seen middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 26.1 positive, the inner seen inner auto-symbol hand.
- Level 25.3 positive, the inner hidden outer auto-symbol hand.
- Level 25.2 positive, the inner hidden middle auto-symbol hand.
- Level 25.1 positive, the inner hidden inner auto-symbol hand.

The positive top hands:

- Level 24 positive, the binary top quantity hands that codes into the perpetual top quality hand.
- Level 23 positive, the top quantity hand that codes into the top quality hand.
- Level 22 positive, the top somewhat quantity hand that codes into the top somewhat quality hand.

The positive upper hands:

- Level 21 positive, the binary upper quantity hands that codes into the perpetual upper quality hand.

- Level 20 positive, the upper quantity hand that codes into the upper quality hand.
- Level 19 positive, the upper somewhat quantity hand that codes into the upper somewhat quality hand.

The positive middle hands:

- Level 18 positive, the binary middle quantity hands that codes into the perpetual middle quality hand.
- Level 17 positive, the middle quantity hand that codes into the middle quality hand.
- Level 16 positive, the middle somewhat quantity hand that codes into the middle somewhat quality hand.

The positive lower hands:

- Level 15 positive, the binary lower quantity hands that codes into the perpetual lower quality hand.
- Level 14 positive, the lower quantity hand that codes into the lower quality hand.
- Level 13 positive, the lower somewhat quantity hand that codes into the lower somewhat quality hand.

The positive switch values:

- Level 12 positive, the separate cycle value that switches to is actually the together moment value.
- Level 11 positive, the mono gap value that switches to is actually the poly cycle value.
- Level 10 positive, the other hour value that switches to is actually the alter gap value.
- Level 9 positive, the fraction minute value that switches to is actually the whole hour value.
- Level 8 positive, the divide second value that switches to is actually the multiply minute value.
- Level 7 positive, the subtract moment value that switches to is actually the add second value.

The positive sync values:

- Level 6 positive, the !all cycle value.
- Level 5 positive, the !most gap value.
- Level 4 positive, the !many hour value.
- Level 3 positive, the !some minute value.
- Level 2 positive, the !least second value.
- Level 1 positive, the !none moment value.

There is the young positive valued linguistics time travelling clock, the young negative valued linguistics time travelling clock, the old negative valued linguistics time travelling clock, and the old positive valued linguistics time travelling clock, where the young positive values become old negative values and the young negative values become old positive values through age transferrance, where the thing that the age is, of the linguistics time travelling clock, is that of a calculator.

Proceed to auto-complete, auto-check, auto-error-correct, and auto-feature these models and associated models contained within and created by this document.

This set is timed as 8:48, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.